

The Photosynthesis of Nicotine.

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In a recent communication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 453) Bhargava and Dhar claim to have obtained "practically pure nicotine hydrochloride" by exposing 2% formaldehyde solution containing ammonia to sunlight or to the light from a mercury arc. Quantities of ammonia varying from 40 to 12.5 c.c. of 6.2 N solution per litre were employed in presence of different catalysts. In all cases nicotine was obtained, and cupric carbonate appeared to be the best catalyst, but in the absence of any quantitative data, it is not clear upon what evidence this statement is based.

In order to separate the nicotine, the alkaline solutions were distilled and the nicotine extracted with ether from the *residue*. Since nicotine is readily volatile with steam it appears improbable that it would be obtained by this procedure even if it were formed. The authors also mention a method of separating hexamethylenetetramine and nicotine by forming the mercuric chloride compound. This appears unnecessary since the former substance is practically insoluble in ether while nicotine is readily soluble.

On examining the data from which the molecular weight was determined, apart from the difficulty of understanding how a value of 158.68 can be deduced from a quantity of 0.0011 g. of platinum, the results appear to have been calculated with the assumption that the formula for nicotine chloroplatinate is $(C_{10}H_{14}N_2)_2, H_2PtCl_6$. No such compound is mentioned in the literature, the most easily formed chloroplatinate being $C_{10}H_{14}N_2, H_2PtCl_6$. 0.0612 G₂ of this would give 0.0210 g. of platinum as compared with 0.0163 g. found by the authors.

To obtain some idea as to the nature of the substances formed in the reaction we conducted an experiment in which 2000 c.c. of 2% formaldehyde and 36 c.c. of 6.2N-ammonia mixed with 5 g. of cupric carbonate were exposed in an open glass trough to the light of a quartz mercury vapour lamp during 60 hours. The solution

was colourless after exposure but when boiled it darkened slightly. After distilling the bulk of the solution the residue was extracted with ether yielding a very small quantity of partially solid material, this was acidified, extracted with a little ether and the aqueous solution made alkaline and again extracted with ether. This ethereal solution left no visible residue on evaporation and on washing the dish with a little water and adding a drop of mercuric chloride solution, no precipitate was formed. The distillate after acidifying with hydrochloric acid and evaporating to dryness yielded a deliquescent salt in appreciable quantity. This smelt of methylamine when treated with sodium hydroxide gave the carbylamine reaction. Mercuric chloride gave no precipitate with the solution and it must be concluded that no nicotine was formed in this experiment.

A similar experiment was conducted with 500 c.c. of the solution to which 0.2 g. of nicotine was added. This was not exposed to ultraviolet light but distilled directly until the volume was reduced to 40 c.c. No nicotine could be detected in the residue. The distillate after acidifying and evaporating gave a picrate and a copious crystalline precipitate with mercuric chloride. It also contained sufficient methylamine, doubtless an impurity in the ammonia, to give the carbylamine reaction.

It is thus not possible to accept the conclusions of Bhargava and Dhar that nicotine is formed by the action of light on formaldehyde and ammonia.

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